

HIPPARCOS

The variation of spherical aberration across the field of view

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The tilted Schmidt corrector of the HIPPARCOS instrument causes considerable off-axis spherical aberration, as pointed out by MATRA (p 39 of the final report, 1980-01-14). Raytracing performed at LO confirms this, but indicates that MATRA has underestimated the effect by a factor -3. The derivation below gives a theoretical estimate in good agreement with the raytracing results, indicating that the effect (if it is considered unacceptable) can only be reduced by reducing either the tilt (i) of the corrector, or the fourth-order figuring of it (γ), or both.

Let $t(a)$ be the thickness of the deposit on the corrector as function of radial distance (a) along the mirror (only points in the yz plane are considered). The angle of incidence for a ray bundle is $(i - \eta)$, where i is the inclination of the corrector and η is the field angle along y axis (neglecting for the moment the slope dt/da). The deposit thus causes a delay by $-2t(a) \cos(i - \eta)$ to the ray incident at point a on the mirror. The impact radius of this ray is $r = a \cos(i - \eta)$, i.e., r is the distance of the ray from the principal ray. The fourth-order figuring of the corrector is given by the term

$$t(a) = \frac{\gamma}{\cos i} (a \cos i)^4 = \gamma \cos^3 i a^4, \quad (1)$$

where, for the present version of the instrument, $\gamma = -0.01465 \text{ m}^{-3}$.

The retardation (wavefront error, W), as function of ray coordinate r , is then

$$\begin{aligned} W(r) &= -2t(a) \cos(i - \eta) = -2\gamma r^4 \frac{\cos^3 i}{\cos^3(i - \eta)} = \\ &= -2\gamma r^4 (\cos \eta + \tan i \sin \eta)^{-3} \\ &\approx -2\gamma r^4 (1 - 3\eta \tan i), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

since η is a small angle. The first term, $-2\gamma r^4$, is the desired figuring to compensate the spherical aberration of the Cassegrain system; the second term gives the variation of spherical aberration with field angle. Putting $W(r) = Ar^4$ we have, theoretically,

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial \eta} \approx 6\gamma \tan i \approx -0.027 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ rad}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

(for $i = 17.125^\circ$). Least-squares fitting polynomials in (x, y) to the wavefront errors W obtained by raytracing yields, at 49 object directions within a $0.9 \times 0.9 \text{ deg}^2$ field, the coefficients A as in the attached figure. The average variation with field angle η is in very good agreement with (3), viz.

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial \eta} \approx -0.025 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ rad}^{-1}.$$

From (3) it appears that the effect can only be reduced by reducing either γ or i , or both. Both could probably be reduced by increasing the length of the instrument ($z_1 =$ distance of primary from corrector), but it is not obvious that the off-axis spherical aberration is very detrimental. At $\eta = \pm 0.00785 \text{ rad}$, i.e. at the very edges of the field, the spherical aberration amounts to about $210 \mu\text{m}/\text{m}^4$, corresponding to a wavefront error of 140 nm at the corners of the pupil ($r = 0.16 \text{ m}$). The maximum transverse aberration is about $7 \mu\text{m}$, or 0.6 arcsec .

	+x						
	-250	-190	-129	-68	-6	56	118
	-256	-195	-135	-74	-11	52	115
	-262	-201	-141	-76	-17	48	111
+y	-268	-207	-146	-85	-21	43	107
	-275	-212	-150	-92	-24	38	101
	-281	-219	-156	-93	-31	31	95
	-286	-224	-162	-100	-37	25	89

Coefficient of $(x^2 + y^2)^2$ (spherical aberration) in polynomial fit to WFE (unit: 10^{-6} m^{-3}).

Variation with η (average): $-0.025 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ rad}^{-1}$.

entrance pupil

angular coordinates in the field

$z = 0$

$z_1 - d$ z^*

z_1 $z_1 + \Delta$

corrector

reference plane

secondary and baffle

primary

focal surface

HIPPARCOS Telescope — Test Version (1980 Oct 15)

(cf Lindegren 1979-12-01 for designations)

f_o (focal length of corrector)	:	666.406569358	m
f_1 (focal length of primary)	:	1.06000603650	m
f_2 (focal length of secondary)	:	-0.628801746112	m
ρ (field curvature radius)	:	1.54934285171	m
d (distance secondary - primary)	:	0.700000000000	m
z_1 (distance corrector - primary)	:	1.300000000000	m
Δ (distance primary - focus)	:	0.133000000000	m
γ (deformation of corrector)	:	-0.014654154759	m^{-3}
b_1 (deform coeff of primary)	:	0.629054408144	
b_2 (deform coeff of secondary)	:	1.87062420755	
f_{eq} (equivalent focal length)	:	2.46512818400	m
h_o (semi-diameter of corrector)	:	0.1600	m
h_1 (semi-diameter of primary)	:	0.1745	m
h_2 (semi-diameter of secondary)	:	0.0668	m
h_α (semi-diameter of field)	:	0.0275	m
η^* (linear obstruction ratio)	:	0.5648	
z^* (distance corrector - baffle)	:	0.7532	m
i (inclination of corrector)	:	0.298887634400	rad (17.125°)
p_x (pupil width, along x)	:	0.1000	m
p_y (pupil half-length, along y)	:	0.1250	m
T_o (max deformation of corrector)	:	2.51	μm
T_1 (max deformation of primary)	:	1.91	μm
T_2 (max deformation of secondary)	:	0.58	μm

	+x						
	50.7	24.4	9.4	0.0	-9.4	-24.4	-50.7
	36.6	15.0	4.7	0.0	-4.7	-15.0	-36.6
	28.2	9.4	1.9	0.0	-1.9	-9.4	-28.2
+y	25.4	7.5	0.9	0.0	-0.9	-7.5	-25.4
	28.2	9.4	1.9	0.0	-1.9	-9.4	-28.2
	36.6	15.0	4.7	0.0	-4.7	-15.0	-36.6
	50.7	24.4	9.4	0.0	-9.4	-24.4	-50.7

$$\eta_{\text{p.r.}} - \eta_{\text{gnom}}$$

INSTRUMENT: 1980 Oct 15 Test Version

Displacement of principal ray from gnomonic projection, in mas (10^{-3} arcsec)

	+x						
	-10.6	-18.5	-26.6	-34.8	-43.2	-51.4	-59.6
	0.2	-7.7	-15.7	-23.9	-32.2	-40.4	-48.6
	11.3	3.6	-4.5	-12.5	-20.6	-28.8	-37.0
+y	22.8	15.2	7.0	-0.6	-8.2	-16.6	-24.7
	34.8	27.4	19.6	11.9	4.2	-3.9	-11.9
	47.3	40.1	32.6	25.0	17.2	9.5	1.6
	60.3	53.3	46.0	38.6	31.0	23.5	15.8

Displacement (along y) of the centre of light from principal ray, in mas.

	+x						
	4.6 2.8	0.4 -2.8	-3.8 -4.4	-7.9 -8.0	-11.8 -11.6	-15.5 -15.2	-18.9 -18.8
	6.5 5.8	2.5 2.2	-1.6 -1.4	-5.7 -5.0	-9.7 -8.6	-13.4 -12.2	-16.9 -15.8
	8.7 8.8	4.8 5.2	0.8 1.6	-3.1 -2.0	-7.0 -5.6	-10.8 -9.2	-14.4 -12.8
+y	11.1 11.8	7.4 8.2	3.3 4.6	-0.2 +1.0	-3.7 -2.2	-7.8 -6.2	-11.4 -9.8
	13.8 14.8	10.4 11.2	6.7 7.6	3.1 4.0	-0.5 +0.4	-4.3 -3.2	-7.8 -6.8
	16.8 17.8	13.7 14.2	10.3 10.6	6.9 7.0	3.4 3.4	-0.2 -0.2	-3.8 -3.8
	19.8 20.8	17.1 17.2	14.1 13.6	11.0 10.0	7.7 6.4	4.2 2.8	0.8 -0.8

Displacement of the first harmonic (spatial frequency 0.09 m, or period 1.146 as at 500 nm wavelength) from principal ray, in mas.

$$\text{Comp. } \Delta y = 1 - 3x + 3.6y$$

$$\text{mean diff. (true } \Delta y - \text{Comp. } \Delta y) = -0.4$$

$$\sigma = \underline{0.9 \text{ mas}}$$

	+x						
	2.1	2.4	2.7	3.0	3.2	3.4	3.5
	1.2	1.5	1.7	2.0	2.2	2.4	2.6
	0.2	0.5	0.7	1.0	1.3	1.5	1.7
+y	-0.7	-0.5	-0.3	0.0	0.3	0.5	0.7
	-1.6	-1.4	-1.3	-1.0	-0.7	-0.6	-0.3
	-2.5	-2.5	-2.3	-2.1	-1.8	-1.6	-1.3
	-3.6	-3.4	-3.3	-3.2	-2.9	-2.7	-2.4

Differential displacement between spatial frequencies 0.10 m^{-1} and 0.08 m^{-1} , corresponding to wavelengths 556 nm and 444 nm, respectively, for the period 1.146 μs (in mas).

	+x						
	2.70	2.48	2.24	1.98	1.72	1.45	1.18
	2.78	2.57	2.34	2.12	1.85	1.58	1.32
	2.85	2.65	2.47	2.16	2.00	1.72	1.46
+y	2.93	2.73	2.54	2.37	2.08	1.87	1.63
	3.01	2.82	2.61	2.56	2.22	2.04	1.82
	3.09	2.93	2.75	2.57	2.41	2.25	2.05
	3.10	2.98	2.85	2.71	2.57	2.44	2.24

Coefficient of $x^2 + y^2$ (focus shift), unit: 10^{-6} m^{-1} .

Coefficient $2.37 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ corresponds to a focus shift $\Delta z = +28.8 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$.

				+x			
	-11.6	-13.5	-15.4	-17.3	-19.2	-21.1	-23.0
	-6.0	-7.8	-9.7	-11.6	-13.5	-15.3	-17.1
	-0.4	-2.2	-3.9	-5.9	-7.8	-9.5	-11.3
+y	5.3	3.5	2.2	-0.2	-2.5	-3.7	-5.4
	10.9	9.1	7.5	5.5	3.6	2.1	0.5
	16.5	14.7	13.0	11.3	9.6	8.0	6.4
	22.1	20.3	18.6	16.9	15.3	13.8	12.3

Coefficient of $y(x^2 + y^2)$ (y component of coma), unit: 10^{-6} m^{-2} .

ζ ↑

← η

Entrance Pupil

Spot diagram for 49 object directions $\zeta = -0.0075 (0.0025) 0.0075$ rad,
 $\eta = -0.0075 (0.0025) 0.0075$ rad (Test Version 1980 Oct 15). Each square
 is 2×2 arcsec².